

Scientific article

Optimal Wind Turbine Cut-Out Speed for O&M Cost-Revenue Balance

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Abstract: *Open electricity markets with high wind power penetration tend to have low prices at high wind speeds, when fatigue loads on turbine components are often highest. This paper, therefore, investigates whether reducing the turbine cut-out wind speed to alleviate fatigue loads and reduce O&M costs is economically viable. We present a techno-economic modelling framework that links fatigue-driven component degradation to O&M costs, and applies it to estimate the net present value of the IEA 22 MW turbine under different market conditions and cut-out wind speeds. Based on the modelling assumptions described in the text, the results indicate that lowering the cut-out speed from 25 m/s to 21 m/s increases NPV by 3.2% in volatile markets, whereas higher cut-out speeds are optimal in fixed-price markets. The results demonstrate the importance of market-aware wind turbine design and control.*

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